

Structural differences in the lower extremities in children aged 7–9 years, caused by playing football: A cross-sectional study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Physical activity during childhood can be beneficial in the long term. However, this practice can influence the child's physiological development. The aim of this study was to determine whether the practice of soccer, in moderation, could be a risk factor for the inadequate development of the lower limb.

Methods: The study group was composed of 115 children, of whom 59 (mean age 8.03 ± 0.89 years) practised soccer 3 times a week and had a positive Physical Activity Questionnaire for Adolescents (PAQ-A) score, while a further 56 (mean age 7.96 ± 0.87 years) did not perform any additional physical activity and had a negative PAQ-A score. A foot posture analysis, based on the foot posture index (FPI), the valgus index, the orientation of the subtalar joint (STJ) and the Q angle of the knee, was carried out.

Results: For the group of soccer players, the following results were obtained: FPI 4.79 ± 2.38 (R) and 3.95 ± 2.31 (L); valgus index $13.56^\circ \pm 1.66^\circ$ (R) and $13.42^\circ \pm 1.48^\circ$ (L); STJ test 79% pronated; Q angle $13.13^\circ \pm 2.06^\circ$ (R) and $13.18^\circ \pm 1.93^\circ$ (L). For the non-players, the corresponding values were: FPI 3.62 ± 2.82 (R) and 3.74 ± 2.77 (L); valgus index $12.76^\circ \pm 1.71^\circ$ (R) and $12.84^\circ \pm 1.72^\circ$ (L); STJ test 50% pronated; Q angle $13.87^\circ \pm 3.01^\circ$ (R) and $13.86^\circ \pm 2.94^\circ$ (L).

Conclusion: There is a degree of difference between the two groups, but the values do not vary greatly from those considered normal for this age group. Any alterations in this respect can be assumed to be caused at older ages than those analysed.